

**ENHANCING THE READING ABILITY OF GRADE TWO TO SIX LEARNERS
THROUGH PROJECT WISER IN A SELECT PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL
IN INFANTA DISTRICT**

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess the effectiveness of Project WISER in enhancing the reading performance of elementary pupils. Employing a One Group Pre-test Post-test Design. Respondents were selected through purposive sampling. Statistical analysis, including mean and t-test, were applied to evaluate the pre-test and post-test results as well as the significant difference between the two tests. Research study's focused solely on the impact of Project WISER on reading performance among Grades Two to Six pupils. Despite the given situation on the low performance among learners in reading, the study conclusively demonstrated that Project WISER significantly contributes to the enhancement of pupils' reading abilities. The findings revealed a notable improvement in reading performance. In the pre-test, elementary pupils demonstrated poor performance, with an average weighted mean of 13.96. However, after the implementation of Project WISER, the post-test results showed a substantial increase, with a weighted mean of 18.53. These outcomes signify that Project WISER served as an effective strategy for developing pupils' reading performance. This research provided insights of using project WISER as an effective reading intervention in developing the reading performance of elementary pupils.

Keywords: *Project WISER, Reading Performance, Reading Difficulties*

INTRODUCTION

The 21st century education is being challenged with most governments around the world have temporarily closed educational institutions in an attempt to contain the spread of the CoVid-19 pandemic. (UNESCO as cited by Borreo & Alva, 2021)

Thus, the suspension of face-to-face instruction in schools during the COVID-19 pandemic has led to concerns about consequences for students' learning. In order to measure and evaluate the effect of school closures on primary school performance, Engzal, et.al.,(2021), conducted a study on the effect of the pandemic to student's learning while at home. The results simply imply that students made little or no progress while learning from home and suggest losses even larger in countries with weaker infrastructure or longer school closures.

Meanwhile, according to Faingold who is currently the chief of United Nations Children's Fund in the Philippines, mentioned that the Philippines was already facing a learning crisis even before the pandemic. For instance, the results of the Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics in 2019, a regional learning assessment designed by and for Southeast Asian countries, revealed that only 10 percent of Grade 5 students in the Philippines met the minimum required standards in reading. He further said that these figures were "significantly low and an issue of concern" as they reconfirmed the results for the secondary level from the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) released in 2018, where the Philippines ranked last in reading. While, the COVID-19 pandemic and other disasters that hit the country worsened the learning crisis in the Philippines. (Philippine Institute for Development Studies, 2022).

In connection to this, PICAB Elementary School conducted a reading assessment on School Year 2022-2023 and it was revealed that out of 720 pupils there are 143 pupils from grades two to six who are non-reader. Thus, to enhance the reading ability of the pupils the researcher implemented Project WISER (Wholistic Individualized Strategies In Enriching Readers) in response to the needs of the pupils.

Research Questions

This research investigation aimed to develop and improve the reading ability of Learner particularly those who are non-reader in PICAB Elementary School using project WISER (Wholistic Individualized Strategies In Enriching Readers). Specifically, this action research sought to answer the following specific questions:

1. What is the performance level in reading of learners before and after implementing the project WISER?
2. Is there a significant difference in the performance level in reading of learners before and after the implementation of project WISER?

4. What are the implications of the findings of this research investigation for the improvement of reading performance of learners in PICAB Elementary School?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research investigation utilized One Group Pre-test Post-test research design since it compared the two set of tests, the pre-test and post-test. According to Thomas (2020), One Group Pre-test Post-test research design aims to establish a cause-and-effect relationship between an independent and dependent variable.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in PICAB Elementary School. The school is located in Brgy. Catambungan Infanta District in the Division of Quezon. The school has 720 elementary pupils, in which 143 pupils from grades two to six fall under the non-reader level in reading.

Respondents of the Study

The participants of this study were those pupils who fall under “Frustration” level in the assessment of reading in PICAB Elementary School from Grades Two to Six. Therefore, there were 143 learners that served as the respondents of this research. Thus, purposive sampling method was employed in this study. Since, purposive sampling in which the researcher selected the members of the respondents based on the objectives of the study (Etikan, Musa, & Alkassim, 2016).

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher secured all the necessary communication with respective authorities before she determined and analyzed the effectiveness of Project WISER (Wholistic Individualized Strategies In Enriching Readers) among grades Two to Six pupils who fall under frustration level in PICAB Elementary School. The researcher conducted parents’ orientation about this research. The Informal Reading Inventory (IRI) was given to the said pupils of PICAB Elementary School twice such as before and after implementing the Project WISER (Wholistic Individualized Strategies In Enriching Readers). Meanwhile, the School Division Office-Quezon’s Informal Reading Inventory (IRI) tool was used to gather the necessary data.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tools were used to interpret the data gathered.

1. **Weighted Mean.** This was used to determine the average reading level of pupils who fall under frustration level in PICAB Elementary School

The formula is:

$$WM = \frac{\sum x}{N}$$

Where:

WM = Weighted Mean

$\sum x$ = summation of weighted frequencies

N = number of cases

To interpret and satisfy the results of the reading level of Grades Two to Six learner of PICAB Elementary School, the School Division of Quezon grading scale below in Informal Reading was used and modified by converting mean percentage scores into the weighted mean scores.

Scale	Interpretation
3.01-4.00	Independent
2.77-3.00	Instructional
0.06-2.76	Frustration
0.00-0.05	non-reader

2. **Paired T-Test.** This was used to analyze and determine the significant difference of the reading ability of Grades Two to Six learners of PICAB Elementary School before and after the implementation implement Project WISER (Wholistic Individualized Strategies In Enriching Reader)

The formula is:

$$t = \frac{\sum d}{\sqrt{\frac{n \sum d^2 - (\sum d)^2}{n - 1}}}$$

Where:

t is the t-value

$\sum d$ is the sum of differences between the pre-test and posttest

$\sum d^2$ is the sum of squared differences between the pre-test and posttest

n is the total number of paired scores

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results and discussion of various data derived in this study concerning the effectiveness of Project WISER in improving the reading skill of grade elementary learners. The results and discussion follow the order of the specific statement of the problem.

Specific Question No. 1. What is the performance level in reading of learners before implementing the project WISER?

Table 1
The Performance Level of Elementary Learners Before the Implementation of Project WISER

No. of Pupils	143
Mean	13.96
Standard Deviation	4.79

Table 1 presents the number of pupils, Mean and Standard Deviation before the implementation of Project WISER. The average weighted mean is 13.96 with a standard deviation of 4.79. The results denote that the average performance of the pupils is not good as revealed in the administered pre-test.

The findings is supported by Faingold who is currently the chief of United Nations Children's Fund in the Philippines who mentioned that the Philippines was already facing a learning crisis even before the pandemic. He further said that these figures were "significantly low and an issue of concern" as they reconfirmed the results for the secondary level from the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) released in 2018 (Philippine Institute for Development Studies,2022)

Specific Question No. 2. What is the performance level in reading of learners after implementing the project WISER?

Table 1
The Performance Level of Elementary Learners After the Implementation of Project WISER

No. of Pupils	143
Mean	18.53
Standard Deviation	3.80

Table 2 presents the number of pupils, Mean and Standard Deviation after the implementation of Project WISER. The average weighted mean is 18.53 with a standard deviation of 3.80. The results denote that the average performance of the pupils is good as revealed in the administered post-test.

The findings of the study are supported by Borreo (2023) who found out that extensive reading remediation made the pupil-respondents improved their oral reading performance. Thus, it depicts that the more that the pupils are exposed to reading sessions, interventions and activities, the more their oral reading improves.

Specific Question No. 3. Is there a significant difference in the performance level in reading of elementary learners before and after the implementation of Project WISER?

Table 3
Test of Significant Difference in the Performance Level of Elementary Pupils Before and After the Implementation of Project WISER

Tests	Average Weighted Mean	P-value	Level of Significance	Decision
Pre-test	13.96	0.00	0.05	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Post-test	18.53			

Table 3 presents the average weighted mean between the performance level in reading of elementary learners in the pre-test, which is 13.96, and 18.53 in the post-test which signifies an increase of 4.57. This was found to be significant as supported by the P-value of 0.00 at a 0.05 level of significance.

The result confirms that there is a significant difference in the performance level in reading of elementary learners of PICAB Elementary School before and after the implementation of Project WISER.

The findings are supported by the study conducted by Tomelden (2019) who used a pretest-posttest experimental approach to perform a study at Lomboy Elementary School with a focus on the efficacy of remedial reading to non-readers in the Intermediate level. The findings revealed that after completing remedial reading exercises using the researcher's methods and strategies, the pupils' reading proficiency had increased. In order for pupils to truly love reading and be supported by a variety of instructional tools, the researcher advised that remedial reading programs be conducted routinely.

Specific Question No. 4. What are the implications of the findings of this research investigation for the improvement of reading performance of learners in PICAB Elementary School?

1. The use of remedial reading provides learners with a valuable opportunity to hone their reading performance.
 2. Learners become more proficient on their reading skills when regular practice in reading is conducted.
 3. Useful and interactive learning materials give learners opportunities to explore their mind while developing their reading skills
 4. Allotted extra time while using reading motivation can motivate learners to engage themselves in class or group activities that will help them to develop their reading skills and fluency.
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Conclusions

The following conclusions were drawn based on the revealed findings of the study:

1. Pupils performed poorly on their reading performance before the conduct of Project WISER.
 2. Pupils performed better on their reading performance after the conduct of Project WISER
 3. The use of PROJECT WISER is an effective way in improving the reading performance of learners
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher sought an approval from the respective authorities first before conducting this research and guaranteed that the participants' identities as well as personal information was kept confidential and unknown.

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